
EMPLOYMENT GENERATION THROUGH MGNREGA IN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract:

The present paper seeks to understand the Concept of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. (MGNREGA) and analysis of the Employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra State. MGNREGA is one the strong tool in the hands rural poor to ensure their employment. Since inception of MGNREGA, It has performed very well in major states of India. The scheme provides guarantee of 100 days of employment to rural poor. In recent days, the wage rate of MGNREGA is increasing in every states of country. Maharashtra is one of the well-developed state in India. MGNREGA in Maharashtra is steady but slowly progressive. The state like Maharashtra has massive potential to enrich MGNREGA employment. MGNREGA is social security for vulnerable section of the society. In Maharashtra state, STs are one step forward to ensure employment through MGNREGA. STs have generated largest person days in employment through MGNREGA in Maharashtra state. However, the MGNREGA should be reached at every section of society so that, all section of the society will ensure their guaranteed employment in Maharashtra state. Therefore, policy makers should take effort to enrich MGNREGA scheme in context of inclusive development and growth of the society.

Keywords: *Concept of Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. (MGNREGA) and analysis of the Employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra State.*

Introduction:

India is developing economy. Unemployment is biggest problem of India because it has second largest population across the world. The most of India's population still lives in rural parts of the country. Besides, Agriculture is one of the major business in rural India. Agriculture is seasonal occupation, it is not able provide employment guarantee to rural

population of India. To overcome the unemployment problem, since government of India has launched various wage employment schemes and rural development programmes. However, India did not get massive success in the field rural employment generation. All the previous schemes and wage employment programmes had not been implemented properly and consistently. Therefore, India

had to be required guarantees wage employment programme. Hence, UPA government introduced one ambitious rural development and wage employment programme which is known as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. (MGNREGA). The MGNREGA has been regarded as a scheme that provides employment during the lean period of agriculture, so that reducing seasonal labour migration from rural to urban areas. The demand for work has larger typically peaks in May- June before falling the subsequent months coinciding with the main kharif cropping season. Therefore, MGNRGA has proven very well to provide livelihood security to especially rural population across the country.

Objectives:

1. To understand the Concept of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme. (MGNREGA)
2. To analyze the Employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra state.

Data Base and Methodology:

The present paper is based on completely secondary data. The required and necessary data concerned Employment Generation Through MGNREGA in Maharashtra have been taken from different sources like books,
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reports articles and internet etc. Similarly, the percentage technique was used to analyze the data.

Interpretation of Data:

The present paper is analyzed by secondary data and some statistical tools like average, standard deviation coefficient of variance and compound annual average growth rate (CAGR) etc. were used to analyze and comparison the available data.

Results and Discussion:

Concept of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA):

The act was notified in 200 district in the first phase with effect from February 2nd 2006 and then it extended to additional 130 districts in the financial year 2007-2008. Four years after it was introduced, the government has decided to rename its flagship rural employment programme after Mahatma Gandhi. PM Manmohan Singh announced on Friday, 2 October 2009 that the NREGA (National Rural Employment Guarantee Act) would now be called Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). A government scheme is being named after the Mahatma after a long time (113 districts were notified with effect from April 1st 2007 and 17 districts in U.P were notified with effect from May 15th 2007) .The rest districts have been

notified under the NREGA with effect from April 1, 2008. Thus, NREGA has been covered the entire country with the exception of districts that have a hundred percent urban population. The Mahatma Gandhi NREGA has been become a powerful tool for inclusive growth in rural India through its impact on social protection, livelihood security and democratic governance. Mahatma Gandhi NREGA was the first ever law internationally that guarantees wage employment at an unprecedented scale. The primary objective of the Act is growing wage employment. Its supplementary objective has strengthening natural resource management through works that address causes of chronic

poverty like drought, deforestation and soil erosion and to encourage sustainable development. The process results include strengthening grass root processes of democracy and infusing transparency and accountability in governance.

Analysis of Employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra:

Maharashtra is one of the developed states in India. More than 50 percent population still lives in rural sector. The state is highest in other economic indicators as well as macro economy policies. There are 35 districts in Maharashtra. MGNREGA is being implemented all the districts of Maharashtra except urban parts.

Table No. 1: Employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra from Financial Year 2014-15 to 2021-22.

Years	No. of Household Provided Employment				Employment for Women	No. of Person days Generated				
	SCs	STs	Others	Total	Women	SCs	STs	Others	Total	Women
2014-15	116230	216827	826553	1159610	965521	6219792	11470200	43691514	61381506	26678743
2015-16	121144	248989	904564	1274697	1085387	7019352	14736040	54573990	76329382	33979769
2016-17	131884	286298	1014509	1432691	1221207	6251719	14352939	50274295	70878953	3179843
2017-18	172286	324505	1200383	1697174	1375142	7983726	16554847	57974560	52513133	37531126
2018-19	199939	341515	1251343	1992797	1450315	8918506	16887114	58781507	84587127	37952068
2019-20	181099	327139	1028929	1537167	1218612	6935102	13173760	42849944	62958806	27332952
2020-21	156406	397755	1130055	1684216	1383579	5888666	19404473	42642014	67935153	29161981
2021-22	183441	385119	1467148	2035708	1627970	6740560	20427486	55363979	82532025	36038486
Average	157803.6	316018.4	1102936	1601758	1290967	6994678	15875857	50768975	69889511	28981871
SD	31466.9	62697.4	204918.7	314494.4	211425.5	1008801	3046819	6874456	10983643	11352340
CV	19.9	19.8	18.6	19.6	16.4	14.4	19.2	13.5	15.7	39.2
CAGR	6.74	8.55	8.54	8.37	7.75	1.16	8.59	3.44	4.32	4.39

Source: Different Years MIS Report of Maharashtra MGNREGA

The above table is indicated that employment Generation through MGNREGA in Maharashtra from Financial Year 2014-15 to 2021-22. The average employment provided to SC household is recorded 157803.6 during the given period. The compound annual average growth rate belonging to SC is 6.74 percent it shows progressive and positive growth in employment of SC during given period. The co-efficient variation of employment of SCs reported to be 19.9 per cent it reflects lower level inconsistency and volatility over the given period of time. Similarly, the average employment provided to STs household is reported 316018.4.6 during the given period. The compound annual average growth rate belonging to ST is 8.55 percent it shows progressive and positive growth in employment of STs and has performed comparatively higher than SC in context of employment provided to households during the given period. The co-efficient variation of employment of STs reported to be 19.8 per cent it reflects lower level inconsistency and fluctuation over the given period of time. Moreover, the average employment provided to others household is recorded 1102936 during the given period. The compound annual average growth rate belonging to Others household is 8.54 percent it shows progressive and positive trend in growth

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of employment of Others household during given period. The co-efficient variation of employment of Others household stood at 18.6 per cent it reflects lower level volatility over the given period of time. Besides, the average employment provided to total household is recorded 1601758 during the given period. The compound annual average growth rate belonging to totals household is 8.37 percent it shows progressive and positive trend in growth of employment of total households during given period. The co-efficient variation of employment of Others household stood at 19.6 per cent it reflects lower level volatility over the given period of time. Similarly, the average employment provided to women is recorded 1290967 during the given period. The compound annual average growth rate belonging to employment provided to women is 7.75 percent it shows progressive and positive trend in growth of employment of women during given period. The co-efficient variation of employment of others women stood at 16.4 per cent it reflects lower level volatility than others over the given period of time.

The average person days generated by SCs registered at 6994678 over the last eight years. The compound annual growth rate of SCs stood at 1.16 percent it shows slow progression of person days generated

in MGNREGA of Maharashtra during the given period. The co-efficient of variation of person days generated by SCs stood 14.4 percent it reflects very low inconsistency over the last eight years in Maharashtra state. Additionally, the average person days generated by STs registered at 15875857 over the last eight years. The compound annual growth rate of STs stood at 8.59 percent it shows positive steady progression of person days generated in MGNREGA of Maharashtra during the given period. The co-efficient of variation of person days generated by STs stood 8.59 percent it reflects very low inconsistency and volatility over the last eight years in Maharashtra state. Besides, the average person days generated by others registered at 50768975 over the last eight years. The compound annual growth rate of others stood at 3.44 percent it shows positive steady progression of person days generated in MGNREGA of Maharashtra during the given period. The co-efficient of variation of person days generated by others stood 13.5 percent it reflects very low inconsistency and volatility over the last eight years in Maharashtra state. Likewise, the average person days generated by totals registered at 69889511 over the last eight years. The compound annual growth rate of totals stood at 4.32 percent it shows positive steady progression of person days generated in MGNREGA of Maharashtra

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during the given period. The co-efficient of variation of person days generated by totals stood 15.7 percent it reflects low inconsistency and volatility over the last eight years in Maharashtra state. And the average person days generated by women are stood at 28981871 over the last eight years. The compound annual growth rate of women's recorded at 4.39 percent it shows positive steady progression of person days generated in MGNREGA of Maharashtra during the given period. The co-efficient of variation of person days generated by women's registered 39.2 percent it reflects relatively higher inconsistency and fluctuation over the last eight years across the Maharashtra state.

Thus, it can be seen here that STs and Others household have been witnessed relatively higher growth in context of number of households provided employment through MGNREGA, whereas STs and Women's have witnessed relatively higher level growth in terms of person days generated in employment provided by MGNREGA across the Maharashtra state during the given period of time.

Conclusion:

MGNREGA is one the strong tool in the hands rural poor to ensure their employment. Since inception of MGNREGA, It has performed very well in major states of India. The scheme provides

guarantee of 100 days of employment to rural poor. In recent days, the wage rate of MGNREGA is increasing in every states of country. Maharashtra is one of the well-developed states in India. MGNREGA in Maharashtra is steady but slowly progressive. The state like Maharashtra has massive potential to enrich MGNREGA employment. MGNREGA is social security for vulnerable section of the society. In Maharashtra state, STs are one step forward to ensure employment through MGNREGA. STs have generated largest person days in employment through MGNREGA in Maharashtra state. However, the MGNREGA should be reached at every section of society so that, all section of the society will ensure their guaranteed employment in Maharashtra state. Therefore, policy makers should take

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